

Suppression of Lithium-Ion Batteries Fire

Muhammad Agung Santoso, Xuanze He, Harry Mitchell, Guillermo Rein

Suppression of Lithium-ion batteries fire can be done by using water, heptafluoropropane (HFC-227ea), fire-extinguishing microcapsules, aqueous vermiculite dispersion (AVD), and F-500 encapsulator agent [1]. Extensive review on the suppression of Li-ion batteries fire can be found in [2]. Water suppression has been reported to required large volume of water (~4000 L of 16 kWh of Li-ion battery [3]) and increased production rate of unwanted gases [4]. An alternative by using heptafluoropropane (HFC-227ea) was investigated by Wang et al. [5], showing that HFC-227ea can quickly extinguished battery fires but should be applied as early as possible and for an extended time to avoid reignition.

A robust way to quickly extinguish battery fires can be conducted by imbedding temperature-responsive microcapsules into the electrolytes and PE separator of the Li-ion battery [6]. The microcapsules contain (1,1,1,2,2,3,4,5,5,5-decafluoro-3-methoxy-4-(trifluoromethyl)-pentane) DMTP extinguishing agent enclosed by an outer layer of poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) (Figure 1a). At high temperature, ~120°C, the PMMA breaks and releases the DMTP to absorb the heat from the fire. Figure 1b shows that the microcapsules decreased the temperature rise of the Li-ion battery, subjected to a standard nail penetration test, up to 74%.

Figure 1. (a) Fire-extinguishing microcapsules. (b) Performance tests of the microcapsule on the Li-ion battery fire by using nail-penetration test. Images source: Yim et al. [6].

To suppress fires from the current common Li-ion battery, which is not equipped with microcapsules, other prospective agents that can be used are Aqueous Vermiculite Dispersion (AVD) compound and F-500 Encapsulator agent. AVD compound is basically a mixture of water and vermiculite which is a clay mineral. As AVD is applied to the battery fire, the water will cool down the fuel and the vermiculite will instantly dry. Because of the high aspect ratio of the vermiculite particle, it will bind together and form a film that separate the oxygen access to the fuel, thus smothering the fires. Wang et al. [7] investigated the performance of AVD on battery fires by comparing the AVD to Novec 1230 and 2-BTP clean fire extinguishing agents. The AVD demonstrated better cooling rate: up to 22°C/s for AVD and 10°C/s for the clean agents. Figure 2 shows the performance of AVD on the extinguishment of a Nickel–Manganese–Cobalt Pouch Cell fires investigated in [7].

Figure 2. (a) Temperatures of the battery during fire experiment without the application of AVD. (b) Temperatures of the battery during fire experiment with the application of AVD. Images source: Wang et al. [7]

F-500 encapsulator agent contains surfactant that reduces the surface tension of the water, so that the water droplets size is reduced and increasing the total heat absorbed by the spray/mist of the agent. The increase of the heat absorbed can be 6 to 10 times of the pure water [1]. In addition, a group of molecules in F-500 forms some sort of encapsulation (or chemical cocooning) around the hydrocarbon molecules so that its flammability is reduced [2] (see also Figure 3). Luo et al. [8] compared the fire-extinguishment performance of F-500, pure water, and anionic nonionic surfactant against Li-ion batteries fire, clearly showing the better performance of F-500 than water alone (Figure 4).

Figure 3. The extinguishment mechanisms of F-500 encapsulator agent of battery fires. Image source: Yuan et al. [2]

Figure 4. The effect of fire-extinguishing agents (F-500, anionic-nonionic surfactant (self-made), and pure water) on battery fires investigated in [8]. Image source: Luo et al. [8].

Reference

- [1] Välisalo, T., 2019, *Firefighting in Case of Li-Ion Battery Fire in Underground Conditions*.
- [2] Yuan, S., Chang, C., Yan, S., Zhou, P., Qian, X., Yuan, M., and Liu, K., 2021, "A Review of Fire-Extinguishing Agent on Suppressing Lithium-Ion Batteries Fire," *J. Energy Chem.*, **62**, pp. 262–280.
- [3] R, T. L. J., Blum, A. F., Bress, T. J., and Cotts, B. R. T., 2013, *Best Practices for Emergency Response to Incidents Involving Electric Vehicles Battery Hazards: A Report on Full-Scale Testing Results*, QUINCY, MASSACHUSETTS, U.S.A.
- [4] Larsson, F., Andersson, P., Blomqvist, P., and Mellander, B.-E., 2017, "Toxic Fluoride Gas Emissions from Lithium-Ion Battery Fires," *Sci. Rep.*, **7**(1), p. 10018.
- [5] Wang, Q., Shao, G., Duan, Q., Chen, M., Li, Y., Wu, K., Liu, B., Peng, P., and Sun, J., 2016, "The Efficiency of Heptafluoropropane Fire Extinguishing Agent on Suppressing the Lithium Titanate Battery Fire," *Fire Technol.*, **52**(2), pp. 387–396.
- [6] Yim, T., Park, M.-S., Woo, S.-G., Kwon, H.-K., Yoo, J.-K., Jung, Y. S., Kim, K. J., Yu, J.-S., and Kim, Y.-J., 2015, "Self-Extinguishing Lithium Ion Batteries Based on Internally Embedded Fire-Extinguishing Microcapsules with Temperature-Responsiveness," *Nano Lett.*, **15**(8), pp. 5059–5067.
- [7] Wang, H., Sun, Q., Guo, J., Xie, S., He, Y., and Chen, X., 2021, "The Efficiency of Aqueous Vermiculite Dispersion Fire Extinguishing Agent on Suppressing Three Typical Power Batteries," *J. Electrochem. Energy Convers. Storage*, **18**(2).
- [8] Luo, W., Zhu, S., Gong, J., and Zhou, Z., 2018, "Research and Development of Fire Extinguishing Technology for Power Lithium Batteries," *Procedia Eng.*, **211**, pp. 531–537.